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YOUTH PERSPECTIVES ON IMPLEMENTING MEASURES TO PREVENT EXTREMISM AND TERRORISM

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Abstract

The article examines the views of young people on measures to prevent religious extremism and terrorism, one of the urgent problems of today. Religious extremism is devotion to extreme views and actions in religion. Signs of extremism characterized by threats, intimidation, aggression and extreme severity and ways to prevent it are sought. Focusing on the concepts of extremism and terrorism, he considers ways to keep young people away from such terrorism.

Keywords: Eextremism, terrorism, young people, to threaten, aggression, extreme severity, state, economy, legal system.

One of the most pressing issues of the 21st century is the threat of religious extremism and terrorism, recognized globally.

Our country's national security is under significant direct threat from incidents such as kidnappings, hostage-taking, hijackings, bombings, violence, ethno-confessional conflicts, and terrorism in general. Non-traditional religious movements, *alien to traditional faith*, are influencing terrorist acts.

In this regard, President emphasized: "Kazakhstan faces problems of terrorism, separatism, and extremism. Considering the broad reach of international terrorism and its connection with the political, social, and economic issues of international communities and regions, the threats posed by it are not imaginary but rather real, tangible threats to life." Therefore, we found it essential to examine this issue as it is one of the most pressing global problems [1].

The legal basis for combating extremism and terrorism in Kazakhstan is established by the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Criminal Code, the Code of Administrative Offenses, and the laws "On Countering Extremist Activities," "On Countering Terrorism," "On the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan," "On the State of Emergency," "On Political Parties," "On Public Associations," and "On Countering Terrorism in the Republic of Kazakhstan." Additionally, cooperation with entities of the Republic of Kazakhstan in counteracting terrorist organizations enables preventative measures aimed at *preventing religious extremism and terrorism, addressing unlawful behavior among students, resolving interethnic conflicts in educational institutions, improving legal consciousness and culture, and fostering tolerance among youth*.

Article 5 of the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan prohibits the establishment and activities of

public associations whose objectives or actions are directed at forcibly altering the constitutional structure, violating the integrity of the country, harming state security, or inciting social, racial, national, religious, clan, and tribal enmity. It also prohibits the creation of militarized groups not foreseen by law. Additionally, Article 10, part 2, specifies that citizens cannot be deprived of their citizenship or right to change their citizenship, nor can they be exiled from Kazakhstan. *Deprivation of citizenship is permitted only by a court decision if an individual commits terrorist crimes or inflicts other serious harm to Kazakhstan's vital interests* [2].

Initially, in July 1999, Kazakhstan adopted the Law "On Combating Terrorism," which defined the legal and organizational foundations for combating terrorism, the procedures for the operation of state bodies and organizations, regardless of ownership, and clarified citizens' rights, obligations, and guarantees related to anti-terrorism efforts [3].

It is impossible to fully understand the concept of "terrorism" without first examining the concept of "extremism," as terrorism is closely linked to extremism—in fact, extremism is a part of terrorism. According to scholars S. I. Ozhegov and N. Y. Shvedova, extremism is defined as follows: "Extremism (French: *extremisme*, Latin: *extremus*—radical) is a tendency to go to extremes (usually in politics)."

In our Criminal Code, the concept of extremism is not explicitly defined. The legislator instead lists the articles of the code that are classified as extremist crimes. For example, according to Article 3, Clause 39 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, "Cases of administrative offenses specified in Articles 174, 179, 180, 181, 182, 184, 258, 259, 260, 267, 404 (second and third parts), and 405 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Kazakhstan are considered administrative offenses" [4].

The essence of extremism is an aggression filled with ideological content (or meaning). In our opinion, extremism signifies acting solely on one's own views, without recognizing general order. Extremism arises from a tendency toward ignorance and excessive views inclined toward fanaticism.

Among such phenomena, terrorism represents a complex, multifaceted, and highly negative socio-political occurrence that transcends national borders, posing a significant threat to the security of the global community. Many international conferences with state leaders have been held to examine effective methods and approaches to counter global terrorism. To oppose terrorism, it is essential that we precisely define its nature. The prefix "religious" indicates adherence to a particular faith. Terrorists do not listen to the guidance of those who point them toward the right path; they consider themselves as the purest and view everyone else as misguided, rejecting knowledgeable people.

Today, terrorism often appears in the forms of political, nationalist, and religious terrorism. Organizers frequently present terrorism as the only possible and most effective way to defend civil or other rights. Its aim is direct pressure on the government or specific political leaders to force a change in policies. Young people from our society frequently become part of terrorist ranks. Due to their youth, upbringing, environment, and worldview, young people become "blind tools" in the hands of extremists, developing a cult of violence toward others, devaluing human life, and fostering cruelty, mutual hatred between nations, and hostility between social groups. By denying everything they encounter in life, young people unwittingly fall into the trap, becoming puppets of terrorist and extremist movements that actively implant distorted perspectives into their minds.

Terrorism is a well-equipped and armed powerful structure. Modern terrorism, with the help of sponsors and donors, is capable of conducting diversionary-terrorist wars in Syria, Iraq, and engaging in large-scale armed conflicts, forming a highly profitable global business (arms supply, drug trafficking, etc.). Speaking of minors and young citizens of Kazakhstan involved in these activities, they represent a serious public danger as they may return to our country with military experience and become field commanders of terrorist groups or leaders of extremist organizations. This situation, we believe, has prompted legislators to consider the issue of revoking the citizenship of such individuals.

In Kazakhstan, religious extremism and terrorism remain critical issues. The rise of religious extremism and terrorism among youth, including children and adolescents, has notably increased crime levels among younger generations. This trend is tied to a shift in the collective consciousness of young people and reflects broader social and political transformations within Kazakh society.

Over the past decade, the qualitative and quantitative composition of extremist organizations has changed dramatically. While it was once thought that religious extremist and terrorist organizations attracted primarily poorly educated or uneducated youth, today

we observe a shift, with these organizations increasingly recruiting well-educated young people, sports professionals, and even officials. This highlights the critical role of the family in shaping young people's personalities. Moreover, it is essential to recognize that the manifestation and development of specific types of Islamic religious extremism in any country or region depend on various factors, including non-Islamic social and economic threats, political and cultural reasons, unemployment, insecurity about the future, alcoholism, and drug addiction. These issues contribute to the growth of unstable or single-parent families, as well as the number of homeless children. In Kazakhstan, it is also essential to note that extremism often aligns artificially with organized crime (including transnational) and with corrupt elites who provide support. Through consistent incitement of intolerance, hostility, and aggression among citizens, social groups, public, and political movements, these groups manipulate diverse cultures, religious beliefs, and mentalities to secure financial gain, safeguard personal power, and ensure the well-being of their loyal followers. The breakdown of families, lack of parental warmth and attention, and societal indifference contribute to filling the ranks of criminals and, consequently, extremists.

Religious extremism takes various forms in its methods of implementation but often manifests as aggressive behavior from a specific social entity. It is characterized by a highly critical perspective toward others (believers), particularly those who do not share the same religious beliefs, combined with self-criticism within the extremist's framework.

The external manifestation of religious extremism includes illegal, violent, destructive, and aggressive acts not only toward others but also toward the extremist believers themselves, sometimes leading to various forms of self-harm, including suicide. Yet, behind the extremist's readiness to persecute and physically eliminate opponents often lies fear and distrust toward the hostile external world.

Moreover, school students, whose mental resilience is still developing and who are highly impressionable, represent a particularly vulnerable environment for the infiltration of religious extremist ideas, including those linked to Islam. Within educational institutions, there are reports of the spread of criminal subcultures. Criminal figures are observed pressuring school students to make financial contributions to a common fund ('общак') to aid people in places of detention, using threats or the possibility of using force.. Furthermore, aggressive, violent, religious beliefs targeting other ethnicities and religious groups also spread within schools.

Among adolescents and youth, extremism, including religious extremism, is often marked by fanaticism, unquestioning obedience to orders that are rarely questioned or debated, and a lack of professional experience or skills. In recent times, the internet has become the most effective tool for terrorists to disseminate information widely among young people. The reasons behind the popularity of the internet among criminals include easy access to a broad audience, anonymous communication, limited state regulation, global reach, high

transmission speed, low cost, ease of use, and a variety of multimedia capabilities.

Extremist resources widely use psychological warfare tools, including disinformation, intimidation, manipulation of public consciousness, and the substitution of concepts and facts. Terrorist organizations' online resources display the psychological harm inflicted on states targeted by attacks [5].

The main characteristics of modern youth extremism include rapidly growing organizational cohesion, a close interconnection of ideas and goals, group solidarity, the formation of ideological doctrines, varied methods for achieving goals using new information technologies and social networks, and strengthened measures of conspiracy.

In Kazakhstan, a system of measures to ensure the security of society and the state from terrorist threats has been developed and gradually improved, allowing for the accumulation of experience in detecting and preventing the activities of terrorist organizations. In recent years, significant work has been carried out to establish and enhance the legislative and organizational framework for identifying and preventing the precursors of terrorism and extremism. Currently, the Republic of Kazakhstan is implementing the State Program for Countering Religious Extremism and Terrorism for 2018–2022 [6].

Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn from the above:

When addressing this urgent global issue, we consider it necessary for governmental authorities, local self-governing bodies, and civil society to undertake the following actions to combat this unfavorable issue:

- Information and Analytical Support for Countering Terrorism and Extremism (producing all possible types of informational materials, such as leaflets, brochures, books, appeals, posters, social advertisements, objective publications about the activities of law enforcement agencies, emergency response centers, and counter-terrorism commissions in the press, as well as creating thematic documentaries and videos);

- Ideological Measures (fostering interfaith and interethnic tolerance, patriotism, a healthy lifestyle, universal human values, and other similar priorities);

- Organizational Measures (assisting the activities of public and religious associations with a focus on counter-terrorism; establishing cooperation with the media; holding conferences, slideshows, roundtable

discussions, competitions for the best anti-terrorism materials, and similar events);

- Educational Direction (creating a training system for specialists in anti-terrorism information activities, including civilian specialists);

- A state program should be adopted to conduct educational work among minors and youth aimed at preventing extremism and terrorism, as well as implementing a set of social rehabilitation measures for individuals remaining in the criminal justice process from the mentioned categories;

- Measures should be implemented to prevent extremist and terrorist activities by religious and other public associations, other organizations, as well as individuals, including identifying, preventing, and stopping extremist and terrorist actions;

In Kazakhstan, a comprehensive approach to combating extremism and terrorism is essential to establish a stable religious environment. Naturally, enhancing its legal framework alongside addressing religious, social, psychological, and economic aspects has become an urgent need of today. As we work to realize the First «Eternal Nation» vision and to build a strong state, it is vital to proactively address each acute issue that threatens national security in a timely manner. After all, «Terrorism does not choose borders or distinguish between rich and poor nations.»

References

1. “Kazakhstan-2050” Strategy: New Political Course of the Established State // http://www.akorda.kz/kz/addresses/addresses_of_president/kazakstan-respublikasynyn-prezidenti-nenazarbaevtyn-kazakstan-halkyna-zholdauly-2012-zhylgy-14-zheltoksan
2. Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan // Adopted by national referendum on August 30, 1995 // <http://adilet.zan.kz/kaz/docs/K950001000>
3. Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan On Countering Terrorism // July 13, 1999, No. 416-I // <http://adilet.zan.kz/kaz/docs/Z990000416>
4. Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan // July 3, 2014, No. 226-V // <http://adilet.zan.kz/kaz/docs/K1400000226>
5. Satpayev, D.A. // Terrorism as a Phenomenon in Political Life, Politics // 1999. No. 3. P. 10.
6. Ilinsky, I.M. // On Terror and Terrorism // Between Future and Past. - Moscow, - Pp. 239, 242.